

Nanobiotechnology and its implementation in Agriculture

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Nanobiotechnology is a pledging field in agricultural research. The current scenario warrants developing countries to develop drought and pest resistant crops, with higher production, therefore, the employment of nanobiotechnology to agriculture and food industries is getting consideration now a day. Researches in agriculture and food nanobiotechnologies are getting importance because their possible advantages vary from augmented food value and safety to lessen agricultural inputs and improve nutrition quality. Nanobiotechnology is a novel scientific approach that involves materials and equipments capable of manipulating physical as well as chemical properties of a substance at molecular levels. On the other hand, biotechnology uses the knowledge and techniques of biology to manipulate molecular, genetic and cellular processes to develop products and services and is used in diverse fields from medicine to agriculture [1].

Agriculture is the backbone of most developing countries, with more than 60% of the population dependent on it for their livelihood [2]. Nanobiotechnology has the capability to transform the agricultural and food industry with innovative tools for the managing diseases, early disease revealing, enhancing the ability of plants to absorb nutrients at molecular level etc. Moreover, nanobiotechnology can advance our understanding of the biology of various crops and thus, can potentially enhance yields or nutritional values, as well as developing improved systems for monitoring environmental conditions and enhancing the ability of plants to absorb nutrients or pesticides when required [3].

Agricultural and food systems security, disease management delivery systems, new techniques for molecular and cellular biology, new materials for pathogen detection and protection of the environment are examples of the important aspects of nanobiotechnology to the science and engineering of agriculture and food systems [4,5]. Though, there are new challenges in this sector including a growing demand for healthy, food safety; an increasing risk of disease; and threats to agricultural production from changing weather patterns [6].

Nanobiotechnology operates at the same level as a virus or disease infecting particle, and thus holds the potential for primordial detection and eradication. It also holds out the possibility that smart sensors and smart delivery systems will help the agricultural industry combat bacteria viruses and other crop pathogens. Long before the symptoms develop, the integrated sensing, monitoring and controlling system could detect the presence of disease and notify the scientist or farmer and activate bioactive systems such as drugs, pesticides, nutrients, probiotics, nutraceuticals and implantable cell bioreactors. In the near future, nanostructured catalysts will be available which will increase the efficiency of pesticides and herbicides, allowing lower doses to be used. Nanobiotechnology will also protect the environment indirectly through the use of alternative (renewable) energy supplies, and filters or catalysts to reduce pollution and clean-up existing pollutants in soil and water. In the agricultural sector, nanobiotech research and development is likely to aid and frame the next level of expansion of genetically modified crops, animal production inputs, chemical pesticides and precision farming techniques [7].

Changes in agricultural technology have been a major factor shaping modern agriculture. Among the latest line of technological innovations, nanobiotechnology occupies a prominent position in transforming agriculture and food production. The development of nanodevices and nanomaterials could open up novel applications in plant biotechnology and agriculture. Currently, the main thrust of research in nanotechnology focuses on applications in the field of electronics, energy, medicine and life sciences [8], as agriculture is not considered as potent industry. While nano-chemical pesticides are already in use, other applications are still in their early stages, and it may take many years before they are commercialized or reached to common man. These applications are largely intended to address some of the limitations and challenges facing large scale, chemical and capital intensive farming systems. This includes the fine tuning

and more precise micromanagement of soils; the more efficient and targeted use of inputs; new toxin formulations for pest control; new crop and animal traits; and the diversification and differentiation of farming practices and products within the context of large scale and highly uniform systems of production. Nanobiotechnology will leave no field untouched by its ground breaking scientific innovations. The agricultural industry is no exception. So far, the use of nanobiotechnology in agriculture has been mostly theoretical, but it has begun and will continue to have a significant impact in the main areas of the food industry: development of new functional materials, product development, and design of methods and instrumentation for food safety and bio-security. The effects on society as a whole will be dramatic.

In the proficient use of agricultural natural assets like water, nutrients and chemicals during farming as nanosensors are user friendly. It makes the use of nanomaterials and global positioning systems with satellite imaging of fields, farmers might distantly detect crop pests or facts of stress such as drought. Nanosensors disseminated in the field are able to sense the existence of plant viruses and the level of soil nutrients [9]. Another aspect, to minimize fertilizer consumption and environmental pollution, nanoencapsulated slow release fertilizers have been widely used [10]. Nanotechnocrats are capable to study plant's regulation of hormones such as auxin, which is accountable for root growth and seedling organization. Nanosensors have been developed that reacts with auxin. This is a step forward in auxin research, as it helps scientists to know how plant roots acclimatize to their environment, particularly to marginal soils [11].

Nanoencapsulation is a process through which chemicals like an insecticide is slowly but efficiently released to a particular host plant for insect pest control. Nanoencapsulation with nanoparticles in form of pesticides allows for proper absorption of the chemical into the plants [8]. This process can also deliver DNA and other desired chemicals into plant tissues for protection of host plants against insect pests [12]. Release mechanisms of nanoencapsulation include diffusion, dissolution, biodegradation and osmotic pressure with specific pH [13,14]. Nanoencapsulation is currently the most promising technology for protection of host plants against insect pests. Now, mostly leading chemical companies focus on formulation of nanoscale pesticides for delivery into the target host tissue through nanoencapsulation.

The easiest way to eliminate weeds is to destroy their seed banks in the soil and prevent them from germinating when weather and soil conditions become favourable for their growth. Being very small, nanobioherbicides will be able to blend with the soil, eradicate weeds in an eco-friendly way without leaving any toxic residues, and prevent the growth of weed species that have become resistant to conventional herbicides. Weeds survive and spread through underground structures such as tubers and deep roots. Ploughing infected fields while removing weeds by hand can make these unwanted plants spread to uninfected areas. On the other hand, nanocapsules can facilitate successful incursion of herbicides through cuticles and tissues, allowing slow and regular discharge of the active substances. This can be act as 'magic bullets', containing herbicides, chemicals origins which target exacting plant parts to liberate their substance [15]. Torney et

al. [16] has exploited a 3 nm mesoporous silica nanoparticle in delivering DNA and chemicals into isolated plant cells. Mesoporous silica nanoparticle are chemically coated and act as containers for the genes delivered into the plants, and triggers the plant to take the particles through the cell walls, where the genes are put in and activated in a clear-cut and controlled way, without any toxic side effects.

Nanotechnology applications have the potential to change agricultural production by allowing better management and conservation of inputs to plant production. Research in nanobiotechnology can do a lot to benefit society through applications in agriculture and food systems [17]. Introduction of any new technology always has an ethical responsibility associated with it to be apprehensive to the unforeseen risks that may come along with the tremendous positive potential. Public awareness about the advantages and challenges of nanobiotechnology will lead to better acceptance of this emerging technology. Rapid testing technologies and biosensors related to the control of pests and cross contamination of agriculture and food products will lead to applications of nanotechnology in the near future.

Nanotechnology has great potential in agriculture as it can enhance the quality of life through its applications in fields like sustainable and quality agriculture and the improved and rich food for community. All over the world, this technology has become the future of any country. One has to be very cautious with any novel technology to be introduced about its probable unforeseen and unexpected jeopardy that could land through its optimistic possibilities. Though, it is also significant for the future of a state to create skilled prospect manpower in this novel technology. Therefore, it becomes vital to inform the common man about its benefits at the first step, which will consequence in incredible augment in the awareness and innovation of novel applications in all the spheres. The outlook of nanobioscience in agriculture is vague owing to lots of grounds, for example the unconstructive response from people towards GM crops, need of lots of required cleverness in government agricultural research and technology units for nano type of explorations and poorly-equipped new instruments and new-fangled technologies. A terrible call for to slash down the jagged outline existing among the society, common man and budding scientific notions and if we achieve something in overcoming this line, then an unexpected bright and beneficial future will be at door step of society.

REFERENCES

1. M. Fakruddin, Z. Hossain, H. Afroz, (2012). Prospects and applications of nanobiotechnology: a medical perspective. *J. Nanobiotechnol.* 10: (2012) 31-35.
2. D.A. Brock, T.E. Douglas, D.C. Queller, J.E. Strassmann, Primitive agriculture in a social amoeba. *Nature* 469: (2011) 393-396.
3. J.C. Tarafdar, S. Sharma, R. Raliya, Nanotechnology: Interdisciplinary science of applications. *Afr. J. Biotechnol.* 12(3): (2013) 219-226.
4. R.M. Welch, R.D. Graham, A new paradigm for world agriculture: meeting human needs, productive, sustainable, and nutritious. *Field Crops Res.* 60: (1999) 1-10.

5. Suman, R. Prasad, V.K. Jain, A. Varma, Role of nanomaterials in symbiotic fungus growth enhancement. *Curr. Sci.* 99: (2010) 1189-91.
6. S.K. Biswal, A.K. Nayak, U.K. Parida, P.L. Nayak (2012). Applications of nanotechnology in agriculture and food sciences. *Int. J. Sci. Innovat. Discov.* 2(1): (2012) 21-36.
7. R. Prasad, U.S. Bagde, A. Varma, Intellectual property rights and agricultural biotechnology: an overview. *Afr. J. Biotechnol.* 11 (73): (2012) 13746-13752.
8. G. Scrinis, K. Lyons, The emerging nano-corporate paradigm: nanotechnology and the transformation of nature, food and agri-food systems. *Int. J. Sociol. Food Agric.* 15: (2007) 22–44.
9. A.G. Ingale, A.N. Chaudhari, (2013). Biogenic synthesis of nanoparticles and potential applications: An eco-friendly approach. *J. Nanomed. Nanotechnol.* 4: (2013) 165-170. doi:10.4172/2157-7439.1000165.
10. M.C. DeRosa, C. Monreal, M. Schnitzer, R. Walsh, Y. Sultan, Nanotechnology in Fertilizers,” *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 5: (2010) 91-94.
11. E.S. McLamore, A. Diggs, P. CalvoMarzal, J. Shi, J.J. Blakeslee, W.A. Peer, A.S. Murphy, D.M. Porterfield, Noninvasive quantification of endogenous root auxin transport using an integrated flux microsensor technique. *Plant J.* 63: (2010) 1004-1016.
12. F. Torney, Nanoparticle mediated plant transformation. *Emerging technologies in plant science research. Interdepartmental Plant Physiology Major Fall Seminar Series.* Phys. p. 696. (2009).
13. W.K. Ding, N.P. Shah, Effect of various encapsulating materials on the stability of probiotic bacteria. *J. Food Sci.* 74(2): (2009) M100-M107
14. R. Vidhyalakshmi, R. Bhakayaraj, R.S. Subhasree Encapsulation the future of probiotics-A Review. *Adv. Biol. Res.* 3(3-4): (2009) 96-103.
15. Pérez-de-Luque, D. Rubiales, Nanotechnology for parasitic plant control. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 65: (2009) 540-545.
16. F. Torney, B.G. Trewyn, V.S. Lin, K. Wang, Mesoporous silica nanoparticles deliver DNA and chemicals into plants. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 2: (2007) 295-300.
17. Sugunan, J. Dutta (2008). *Nanotechnology Vol. 2: Environmental Aspects* (Krug Harald (ed.), Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, (2008).

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